

CITINET: LEARNING TO PERCEIVE THE NETWORK CITY IN COLLABORATION

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Abstract

CITINET is a joint learning space which was first carried out by three schools of architecture in Spain and Brazil in the academic year 2013-14. The purpose of the activities included in this learning space was to analyze and represent the contemporary city by means of photographic media. CITINET is a derivation of the blended-learning model established by the course Systems of Representation which has been taught at the School of Architecture La Salle since 1999. A joint structure of learning activities have been performed by the students of the three schools using a common web-based learning environment. Each school has applied different strategies to adapt this joint structure to their own courses. The reflections on the results obtained will help to develop strategies to reinforce the process of collective knowledge construction initiated in this first implementation.

Keywords: Photography, city image, architecture, learning design, blended-learning, knowledge construction

1 INTRODUCTION

The course Systems of Representation (SDR) has been taught in the School of Architecture La Salle since the academic year 1999-2000 (www.salleurl.edu/sdr). More than a course in the traditional sense, SDR is an open and participative space of knowledge construction that integrates different subject-matters: theory of art and architecture, aesthetics and composition, graphic design and visual communication, visual studies and representation. It is divided into six themes, each one standing for a system of representation: Text, Figure, Object, Image, Space and Light. The interrelationship between the various subjects embraced by the course gives rise to a space of knowledge that transcends disciplinary boundaries. The collaborative construction of relationships among the different areas of knowledge, carried out by students and teachers, is a major goal of the course. A web-based environment – the web-based learning environment SDR: NETWORKING, especially conceived for this course by the research group ARC Engineering and Architecture La Salle (www.salleurl.edu/arc)– has enabled students to participate in the process of knowledge construction [1].

In the academic year 2013-14, we initiated a process to share the methodology and learning resources of the course with other institutions using the web-based learning platform – re-named as SDR:NET in its latest version– to design new joint learning spaces in collaboration with other schools of architecture. An initial experience in this regard has been “CITINET: Perception and analysis of the networked city through photography”, a learning space that has been shared with the School of Architecture San Jorge, Zaragoza, in Spain and the Faculdade de Arquitetura e Urbanismo (FAU), Universidade de São Paulo (USP), in Brazil (Fig. 1). The collaborative learning activities were carried out the web-based learning platform SDR:NET developed by the research group ARC Engineering and Architecture La Salle (www.salleurl.edu/sdr). One hundred and twenty students and six teachers from the three schools participated in the activities that took place in the second semester.

Figure 1. Poster of CITINET / ARQUIGRAFIA produced by the Faculdade de Arquitetura e Urbanismo, Universidade de São Paulo

1.1.1 Integrating different courses in a common learning space

The purpose of the CITINET was to create a collaborative learning space which brings together the courses taught at each of the three participating schools. This shared learning space has been developed in parallel to the academic program of each school. In each school, different strategies have been adopted to foment link the activities at each course with the collaborative work carried out in CITINET.

SDR is a compulsory course at the School of Architecture La Salle which is taught in the third year of five-year professional program. The theme Image has been dedicated to providing architecture students with the capacities that enable them to understand the world mediated by image, and to develop their abilities to think and communicate using photographic images. The photographic image is addressed in this course from a multidisciplinary perspective, embracing its technical (mechanical and digital photography), philosophical (idea and image), aesthetic (photography as art, photography with regard to painting and architecture) and cultural (history of photography, advertising) dimensions. The tasks given to students were to learn to perceive images in the contemporary visual environment (mediascape), in the urban environment (mediascape), and to establish links between both [2]. This program, carried out in the last years in various formats within the courses at La Salle, has been the direct precedent of the CITINET learning space. Ninety-five students participated in the common learning activities over six weeks.

In the School of Architecture San Jorge, in Zaragoza, the participation in CITINET was an opportunity to introduce photography into the academic program. The activities were carried out within the undergraduate course “Form Analysis” which takes place in the second semester and which is dedicated to introducing students to some of the fundamental concepts of architecture, such as learning to understand architectural precedents. The learning activities planned in CITINET became one of the exercises of the course and were carried out during three weeks by ten students.

At the Faculdade de Arquitetura e Urbanismo, Universidade de São Paulo, the activities of CITINET were carried out as part of the elective subject “Taller CITINET-ARQUIGRAFIA” addressed at Bachelor students –from different course levels– of the Architecture and Urbanism program. The goal of the course was to foster a critical reflection on the role of photography and digital media in conjunction with the reading of texts in a collaborative working environment, interacting with the two Spanish schools. Students used two learning platforms: ARQUIGRAFIA (www.arquigrafia.org.br) developed by the NAWEB – Núcleo de Pesquisa em Ambientes Colaborativos na Web (<http://nap.usp.br/naweb>), used in their course, and the SDR:NET platform. Thirty students participated in the activities.

1.2 CITINET: analyzing the city through photography

We live in a culture dominated by image. The ubiquity of the image in all realms of our life calls for new theoretical frameworks which enable us to understand the richness of the visual experience [3]. This requires approaches to address the image from a multidisciplinary perspective, such as the one postulated by the field of Visual Studies. According to Rodowick [4], "Visual studies hold together as a discipline through a consensus based on recognizing commonalities among "visual" media –painting, sculpture, photography, cinema, video and new media – and the critical theories that accompany them." In accordance with this approach, CITINET has been conceived as a learning space dedicated to analyzing the global dimension of the contemporary city, using photography as an instrument of reflection, analysis and communication. In this context, photography is considered a tool to develop the ability to perceive and understand the urbanscape in its different scales - the territorial structure, the urban landscape, the spaces shaped by buildings, the objects that make up the city (buildings, infrastructure, urban furniture) as well as the interaction between people and the spaces they inhabit (the atmosphere of the streets and squares, the character of the neighbourhoods, the absence of the no-places).

Today's cities are constantly generating and broadcasting images. The flow of images, disseminated through multiple media –advertising, film, printing, digital networks– is permanent. Cities and buildings have become "iconic" to facilitate their dissemination through the media. In this context, photography – this means, the production and dissemination of "photographic" images within produced and disseminated with the aid of digital tools and networks– becomes a nexus between the city and other image-producing realms such as art and advertising. In this context, capturing and representing the contemporary city through photography is not limited to developing an ability to understand the mutual interaction between the form of buildings and the spaces they define. Furthermore, it requires an understanding of the mechanisms of production and interpretation of photography in contemporary image culture.

1.2.1 Learning design

The pedagogical model of CITINET is based on a blended-learning approach, which integrates the activities carried out in the shared learning space –that is, the web-based learning environment SDR:NET– with the activities done in each of the courses at the participating institutions. The learning activities are organized into sequences, which can be carried out synchronously or a-synchronously by the participating schools.

Figure 2. Structure of the shared learning activities

In this first edition of CITINET, the activities have been organized in three sequences (Fig. 2):

- Perceiving, activities aimed to represent cities and relationships between cities by means of photographs
- Reflecting, deriving ideas from the collection of city images collaboratively produced by the participating students

- Communicating, disseminating the ideas and images about the contemporary city both in specific locations –through local exhibitions– and in a joint publication.

SDR:NET, developed by the research group ARC Engineering and Architecture La Salle (www.salleurl.edu/arc) is the environment that facilitates the collaborative design of the learning activities and their execution by students from the different schools (Fig. 3). Learning tasks can be defined in multiple ways according to the specific pedagogic objectives and submission formats. Students have uploaded their photographs to this learning environment and the associated texts and concepts. Then, they have used the tools that SDR: NET provides to group, compare and relate images from the three analyzed cities, Barcelona, Zaragoza and Sao Paulo. Besides, students and teachers from the three schools could comment and assess the submitted works. These activities, carried out in the shared learning space, enabled learners –students and teachers– to participate in a collaborative knowledge construction process about the contemporary city.

Figure 3. Entry page of the learning environment SDR: NET

The sequences of learning activities were carried out in the second semester, between March and May 2014. The time plan of two schools –La Salle and FAU- was quite similar; while the third one – San Jorge- started its activities when the other two were finishing them (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Planning of the activities at each participating school

This lack of coincidence in time was not necessarily an obstacle for collaboration. While the two schools working simultaneously would benefit from mutually discussing the results as they were being presented by students in Barcelona and Sao Paulo, the students from Zaragoza would benefit from the repository of ideas and images stored in the web-based learning environment SDR: NET. At the end of the process, in the month of May, a joint review of the work of the three schools was performed via teleconference. Finally, to end with the process of convergence, a joint publication was produced with the inputs of students from the three schools.

1.2.2 Learning activities

The learning activities which were carried in the three sequences are described below.

Learning sequence: PERCEIVING

- Learning activity 1: Representing

The task is to take five photographs of the city that express some of the ideas about the contemporary city that as described in the text “The Generic City” by Rem Koolhaas [5]. This requires participants to read, understand and discuss the text in the classroom and to apply the conceptual framework – the ideas proposed in the text- to the vision of the city, mediated by photography. This activity puts into relation the actual city, the theoretical framework provided by the text, and the photographs produced by students. Concepts derived from the reading of Koolhaas’ text were attached to the photographs. A short text describing the relationship between the concept and the photograph was also included.

As a result of this activity, a digital library of images and a vocabulary of concepts derived from Koolhaas’ text associated to them was created in SDR:NET. Images could be browsed in multiple ways: by concept, by city and by author (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. SDR: NET Result of the activity “Representing”

- Learning activity 4: Combining

The task consisted in finding photographs of one’s city which are induced by the images and/or ideas borrowed from another city. The objective of this activity was to exchange ways of looking from one city to another. The photographic medium does not only enable the transposition of images from one place to another (from one city to another, from one medium to another), but also to transpose a way of looking across places. For instance, to look to Barcelona as if it were be Sao Paulo, or vice versa (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. SDR: NET Result of the activity “Combing”

Learning sequence: REFLECTING

- Learning activities 2-3. Comparing and grouping

Having created a collective digital library of city photographs and associated concepts from Koolhaas' text, the next task was to find out and explain the relationships between the photographs, either between the same cities or from several cities. The relationships were created in two ways: by comparing and describing the idea of the city portrayed in the photographs, and by creating a group of photographs that shared the same concept about the city. In both cases, the relationships had to be described with a short text. The ideas that students derived from the photographs gave rise to a network of ideas and images relating the three cities (Fig. 7-8).

Figures 7-8. SDR: NET Results of the activities “Comparing” and “Grouping”

Learning sequence: COMMUNICATING

- Learning activity 4. Publishing

To conclude the activities carried out by the three schools, a publication that summarized the ideas collectively developed was produced. Students could use any image or text submitted to the SDR:NET environment to express their ideas on the contemporary events in an A4 layout. The objective of the tasks was twofold: to translate ideas from one medium to another –from the web-based learning environment onto a book– and to use the collective work –photographs, texts produced by all three schools- as a knowledge repository to be elicited (Fig. 9).

Figure 9. Joint publication of collective outputs

To conclude the joint activities, a final critique was carried out via teleconference with the participation of the teachers and students from the three groups (Fig. 10). In this session, students presented their work and teachers made comments on their work.

Figure 10. Final critique via teleconference with the participation of students and teachers from the three schools

2 DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

The learning activities described in the previous section were carried out by three partners, although adapted to the specific needs of each course. The discussion in the classroom of the text from Rem Koolhaas was the common starting point in the three schools. In the San Jorge School of Architecture, the text was discussed along with other texts from Michel Foucault [6] and Marc Augé [7] about heterotopic spaces and non-places respectively. The Faculdade de Arquitetura e Urbanismo undertook a critical discussion about the intrinsic contradictions of the terms used by Koolhaas – centrality, for instance– which can have opposing meanings depending on their interpretation. Along

this line, the task given to students was to identify images of Sao Paulo that both confirm and contradict the characteristics of the generic city. To reinforce the idea of the multiplicity of links that can exist texts and images, the poem 'Cidade City Cité' from Augusto de Campos, 1963, was introduced to students. Regardless the different approaches adopted by each schools with regard to the common initial task –to discuss Koolhaas' text–, all students carried out the common learning activity “Representing”, which was delivered in the SDR:NET learning environment.

Some of the tasks to be carried out in SDR:NET were specifically designed to foster the exchange of knowledge and ideas among the three institutions. The activity “Combining” is the clearest example in this regard. To carry out this activity, students had to identify an image from one city and derive from them a way to looking at their own city. In some cases, the relationships that were proposed were straightforward either because the images were very similar and/or because the associated concept was the same (Fig. 11)

Figure 11. “Combining”: Similarity of images and concepts in the three cities.

In other cases, the connections established by different students relating images from the three cities gave rise to a network of concepts representing a networked, global city. For instance, a student from La Salle related the concept “Infrastructures” associated to a photograph of Barcelona with the concept “Connected” as illustrated by a photograph of Zaragoza (Fig. 12). A second La Salle student proposed a relationship between a “Connected” Barcelona with the “Infrastructures” of Sao Paulo. The three cities –Barcelona, Zaragoza, Sao Paulo– were interrelated through two concepts –“Connected”, “Infrastructures” – in a network built with the collaboration of students of the three schools –those who did the photographs, and those who related them to other images.

Figure 12. “Combining”: Similarity of images and concepts in the three cities.

Similarly, the learning activities “Comparing and grouping” contributed to forge a network of ideas and concepts interlinking the three cities, as described and visualized by students. “Grouping” enabled to group cities –as represented by the photographs taken by students– under a common category or idea proposed by the student that makes the group.

The task to connect ideas, images and cities was continued right up until the last activity, “Publishing”. In these cases, the space where images and concepts were brought together was a page. Similarities could be found not only on an urban scale but also at other levels, architectural, cultural and even geometrical by arranging images in the page (Fig. 13). In other cases, the meaning of a photograph and the words place together with it complemented each other (Fig. 14).

Figure 13. "Publishing": Proposing geometrical relationships

Figure 14. "Publishing": Complementary meanings of images and texts

The realization of these activities have contributed to fostering the relationships between cities and schools and students and teachers. The use of a common web-based learning environment has facilitated this exchange. However, the full potential of the outcomes produced has not been fully exploited. It would have been necessary to discuss the network of relationships collectively built in the classroom –and in joint teleconferences.. This requires time to identify critical issues and to bring them forward for further discussion. Without a subsequent reflection on the work presented by students in the web-based learning environment, it is likely that their value remains hidden in the submissions. To bring them to the light, the submitted work needs to be taken as one more learning resource to carry out an additional learning activity, either in the classroom and/or in the web-based environment.

3 CONCLUSIONS

This first to design and implement a common learning space juxtaposed to the academic activities carried out in three separate courses at three different institutions has been carried out successfully: the three schools have shared a common structure of learning activities which have been implemented using a common learning platform, the web-based learning environment SDR:NET. This platform has enabled some collaborative work, mostly asynchronous, which has facilitated the exchange of ideas across students, courses and schools. This collaborative dimension of the learning activities could be reinforced in later editions, through joint live sessions via teleconference and by designing new tasks to be carried out by teams made up of students from different schools. In a further step in this process, it needs to be seen if the three autonomous courses can derive in a more integrated program, in which students acquire similar learning outcomes and are granted a similar number of credits for the activities done in CITINET.

REFERENCES

- [1] Madrazo, L.. (2003). SDR: NETWORKING. A web-based learning environment to promote interdisciplinary and participatory education in the information age. Proceedings of the CSCL, Computer Supported Collaborative Learning, Bergen, Norway.
- [2] Madrazo, L. (ed.) (2009). Barcelona Reflections. Images of the Contemporary City. Ingeniería i A Arquitectura La Salle.
- [3] Mirzoeff, N. (1999). An Introduction to visual culture. New York: Routledge.
- [4] Rodowick, D.N. (2001). Reading the Figural. Or, Philosophy after the New Media. Durham & London: Duke University Press.
- [5] Koolhaas, R. (1995). The Generic City. In R. Koolhaas, & B. Mau, S,M,L, XL. The Monacelli Press.
- [6] Foucault, M. (1986). Of Other Spaces. Diacritics, vol. 16, no.1, pp. 22-27.
- [7] Augé, M. (1995). Non-places : introduction to an anthropology of supermodernity. London ; New York : Verso.